

Reaction of Aniline with Steroidal α -Epoxides

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A number of methods have been reported for opening of the steroidal α -epoxidizing leading to the formation of aziridines by cyclisation of the open-chain compounds. The aziridines find application as pharmaceutical, veterinary medicines and agro chemicals¹. Ducker and Lazer² reported the preparation of *N'*-aziridines from β -epoxides by reaction of acetonitrile in presence of BF_3 followed by treatment with alcoholic base, while Shafiullah and Husain³ prepared aziridines by reaction of α -epoxides of cholesterol derivatives with acrylonitrile in presence

of BF_3 -etherate followed by treatment with alcoholic NaOH . We carried out reaction of the steroidal α -epoxides (1-3) with aniline to obtain the corresponding aziridines under similar reaction conditions, but rather than getting aziridines as the final products we have only obtained the open-chain products (4-6). In case compound 4, the acetoxy group is hydrolysed into corresponding alcohol (7) under the basic conditions used for the cyclisation to form aziridines. The physical and spectral data (Table 1) confirm the assigned structures.

TABLE I—PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 4-7

Compd. no	M.p °C	ν_{max} (cm^{-1})	δ	<i>m/z</i>
4	129	3 470 (OH), 3 420 (NH), 1 740, 1 250 (CH_3CO_2), 1 610 (db), 1 510, 740 (Ph)	7.10 (t, NHC_6H_5), 6.53 (NHC_6H_5), 5.11 (C_3 - α H, $W_{1/2}$ 20 Hz), 3.29 (C_6 - α H), 1.91 (s, CH_3CO_2), 1.18 (C_{10} - β CH_3), 0.62 (s, C_{13} - β CH_3)	538, 537, 325, 324, 118, 93
5	157	3 370 (NH), 3 520 (OH), 730 (Cl), 780, 1 570 (Ph)	7.10 (t, NHC_6H_5), 6.54 (br, NHC_6H_5), 4.28 (m, C_3 - α H), $W_{1/2}$ 19 Hz), 3.28 (br, C_6 -H), 1.20 (s, C_{10} - β CH_3), 0.63 (s, C_{13} - β CH_3)	515, 513, 460, 325, 324 (base peak), 132, 118, 92
6	243	3 350 (NH), 3 470 (OH), 1 570, 780 (Ph)	7.08 (t, NHC_6H_5), 6.56 (NHC_6H_5), 4.08 (m, C_3 - α H), 3.28 (br. s, C_6 -H), 1.18 (s, C_{10} - β CH_3), 0.73 (s, C_{13} - β CH_3)	524, 523, 434, 430, 361, 358 353, 352, 138, 104, 86, 70, 57 (base peak)
7	202	3 530 (OH), 3 410 (NH), 1 600 (db), 1 505, 745 (Ph)	7.06 (t, NHC_6H_5), 6.02 (NHC_6H_5), 4.01 (br m, C_3 α - H), 3.29 (C_6 -H), 1.18 (s, C_{10} - β CH_3), 0.62 (s, C_{13} - β CH_3)	497, 495, 406, 234, 132, 118, 93, 56

All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

Experimental

The melting points were determined on a Boetius apparatus and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 237 spectrophotometer, pmr spectra (CDCl₃) on a Varian A-60 spectrometer (60 Hz) and mass spectra on a Jeol-D 300 spectrometer at (70 eV).

3β-Acetoxy-5,6α-epoxy-5α-cholestane (1), 3β-chloro-5,6α-epoxy-5α-cholestane (2) and 3β-hydroxy-5,6α-epoxy-5α-diosgenin (3) were prepared by standard method⁴.

Reaction of α-epoxide (1) with aniline-BF₃ etherate : Boron trifluoride-etherate (2 ml) was added

dropwise over 15 min to a stirred suspension of α-epoxide (1) (m.p. 98°; 2.0 g in dichloromethane) and aniline (2 ml). The resulting solution was further stirred for 25 min and then washed with water, 10% HCl and water and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. Removal of the solvent provided an oily mass which was chromatographed over silica gel column (40 g). Elution with hexane-ether (8 : 1) provided a white solid which on crystallisation from light petroleum ether afforded crystalline solid (4; 1.5 g), m.p. 129°.

Reaction of compound 4 with alcoholic NaOH : Compound 4 (1.1 g) was dissolved in absolute ethanol followed by addition of alcoholic NaOH (10%; 20 ml). The mixture was refluxed for 3 h, then acidified with ether, the ethereal layer washed with water and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. Evaporation of the solvent afforded an oil which on crystallisation from ethanol gave colourless crystals of 7 (0.8 g), m.p. 202°.

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